

S-BENZYL THIURONIUM DERIVATIVES OF OXYMETHYLENE KETONES

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S-Benzyl thiuronium chloride reacts in aqueous alcoholic solution with oxymethylene ketones to form well defined crystalline derivatives. In some cases the sodium compounds of the oxymethylene ketones, formed in their preparation, directly react with the reagent whereas in others the ketones must first be exactly neutralised with caustic soda or caustic potash and then made to react with the reagent.

Donlavy (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1009) has shown that *S*-benzyl thiuronium chloride (I), prepared from benzyl chloride and thiourea, reacts readily in aqueous alcoholic solution with sodium or potassium salts of organic acids to give crystalline derivatives (II) which may be used to characterise the acids. The reaction proceeds rapidly and in a short time the crystalline derivative (II) is deposited.

It has been shown by Claisen (*Ber.*, 1887, **20**, 2191; 1888, **21**, 915) that the formyl derivatives (IV) of a ketone (III) exist mostly as their enols (V) known as oxymethylene ketones which are strongly acidic and are comparable in this respect to true organic acids.

It was, expected, therefore that the sodium compounds of these ketones (V) would also react with *S*-benzyl thiuronium chloride (I) to give the corresponding derivatives. The preparation of organic derivatives of oxymethylene ketones is important for two reasons. Firstly many of these oxymethylene ketones are unstable and cannot be preserved. They readily undergo self-condensation to form trisubstituted benzenes (Claisen and Stylos, *Ber.*, 1888, **21**, 1145; Kaushal, Sovani and Deshapande, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **19**, 115).

If therefore they could react in the form of their sodium salts, which are stable with *S*-benzyl thiuronium chloride, a stable organic derivative could be obtained. For example, the sodium salt of oxymethylene acetone (V, R=CH₃; R'=H) could give *S*-benzyl thiuronium oxymethylene acetate (VI, R=CH₃; R'=H).

Secondly since Donlavy (*loc. cit.*) has shown that some of these *S*-benzyl thiuronium derivatives of organic acids (II) are readily hydrolysed, such derivatives, if they could

be formed from oxymethylene ketones, would serve the purpose of isolation and purification of such ketones.

When the sodium salt of oxymethylene acetone is suspended in absolute alcohol and an alcoholic solution of the reagent (I) is added, the derivative (VI, $R=CH_3$; $R'=H$) begins to appear in the crystalline form. Freed from sodium chloride and crystallised from alcohol the compound separates in needles, m.p. 140° .

In the case of oxymethylene methylethyl ketone (V, $R=R'=CH_3$) (cf. Kaushal *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **18**, 481; 1942, **19**, 116; 1943, **20**, 55) the derivative (VI, $R=R'=CH_3$) has been prepared by two methods. In one method the sodium salt of the ketone (V, $R=R'=CH_3$) is directly treated with the reagent in alcoholic suspension. In the other the ketone is made exactly neutral by the addition of caustic soda and to the aqueous solution so formed the reagent dissolved in alcohol is added. In both the cases the same compound (VI, $R=R'=CH_3$) is formed but the yield in the latter method is better. The pure compound crystallises from alcohol and melts at $67-68^\circ$.

Oxymethylene acetophenone (V, $R=C_6H_5$; $R'=H$) gives the derivative (VI, $R=C_6H_5$; $R'=H$) which crystallises from ethyl acetate, m.p. 190° .

Oxymethylene cyclohexanone neutralised with aqueous caustic potash or soda yielded the derivative (VII) which when crystallised from alcohol melts at 120° .

Similarly oxymethylene menthone gives the derivative (VIII) melting at 203° . In the case of oxymethylene cyclohexanone and oxymethylene menthone the solid sodium compounds formed in their preparation fail to give any yield. The derivatives could be obtained only through the ketone neutralised with caustic potash or caustic soda.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Preparation of S-Benzyl Thiuronium Chloride (I).—Benzyl chloride (12.6 g.), thiourea (7.6 g.) and absolute alcohol (200 c.c.) were mixed together and refluxed on a water-bath. At first the thiourea remained undissolved but after about half an hour a vigorous reaction set in and the whole of the thiourea was dissolved. The reaction subsided after 1 hour and the contents were heated for 1 hour more and poured hot in a beaker, when *S*-benzyl thiuronium chloride separated on cooling. The crude product was crystallised from absolute alcohol as shining plates, m.p. 174° , yield 15 g.

The *oxymethylene ketones* in general were prepared by Claisen's method using 1 mol. of ketone, 1.5 mols ethyl formate and 1.5 atoms of sodium wire in ether under ice-cooling. The sodium compounds, thus formed, were washed from organic matter and used as such. In some cases the sodium compound was decomposed with cold dilute sulphuric acid and the oxymethylene ketone extracted with ether and purified further.

S-Benzyl thiuronium oxymethylene acetate (VI, $R=CH_3$; $R'=H$) was obtained in good yield by reacting sodium oxymethylene acetone, suspended in alcohol, with the reagent dissolved in minimum quantity of absolute alcohol in molecular proportion and keeping the reaction mixture for some time when the derivative separated as colourless prisms. Crystallised from absolute alcohol it melts at 140° . (Found: N, 10.8; S, 12.9. $C_{12}H_{16}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 11.1; S, 12.7 per cent.)

Reaction of Oxymethylene Methylene Ketone (V, $R=R'=CH_3$) with *S-Benzyl Thiuronium Chloride*.—A dilute solution of caustic soda (1.7g.) was added to oxymethylene methyl ethyl ketone (3 g.) when a clear solution was obtained. To it 6 g. of the reagent dissolved in minimum quantity of absolute alcohol were added and the mixture allowed to remain when after sometime a crystalline derivative separated which was filtered, dried and recrystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. $67-68^\circ$; yield about 2 g. (Found: N, 10.9; S, 12.3. $C_{12}H_{18}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 10.5; S, 12.0 per cent.)

The *derivative* (VI, $R'=H$; $R=C_6H_5$) from oxymethylene acetophenone (V, $R=C_6H_5$; $R'=H$. Bülow and Sicherer, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 3891) with the reagent (I) was prepared by treating oxymethylene acetophenone (3 g.) as in the previous case with sodium hydroxide (1.1 g.) and 4.1 g. reagent when a crystalline derivative was obtained, which was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 190° , yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 9.6; S, 10.6. $C_{17}H_{18}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 8.9; S, 10.2 per cent.)

Reaction of S-Benzyl Thiuronium Chloride with Oxymethylene cyclohexanone.—Oxymethylene cyclohexanone, b.p. $79^\circ/4$ mm. (2.5 g.) (*cf.* Wallach, *Annalen*, 1903, 329, 109) was exactly neutralised with a dilute solution of 1.1 g. caustic soda and 4 g. of the reagent dissolved in the minimum quantity of absolute alcohol were added when the crystalline derivative (VII) was obtained on standing. It was filtered, dried and recrystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 120° ; yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 10.0; S, 10.8. $C_{15}H_{20}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 9.6; S, 10.9 per cent.)

Reaction of S-Benzyl Thiuronium Chloride with Oxymethylene menthone.—Oxymethylene menthone was prepared by the method described by Bishop, Claisen and Sinclair (*Annalen*, 1894, 281, 394), b.p. $111-112^\circ/5$ mm. and 1.5 g. of it were exactly neutralised with a dilute solution of 0.9 g. caustic soda when a clear solution was obtained. To this 1.7 g. of the reagent, dissolved in the minimum quantity of absolute alcohol, were added and the mixture allowed to remain when a crystalline derivative (VIII) separated in small quantity. It recrystallised from absolute alcohol as almost colourless needles, m.p. 203° , yield 0.5 g. (Found: S, 9.5. $C_{18}H_{24}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 9.2 per cent.)

